

Comparison of 3 Dynamic Borrowing Approaches to Augment Time-to-event Endpoint in a Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial

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Abstract

There has been a growing interest in dynamic borrowing for clinical trials in that how much external information to borrow can be properly determined by actual scenarios. Several Bayesian and frequentist dynamic borrowing approaches have been developed for randomized controlled clinical trials with time-to-event endpoints. In this paper, three propensity score-integrated dynamic borrowing approaches are evaluated: 1) Commensurate prior method; 2) Conditional borrowing with resampling method; 3) Propensity score-integrated Kaplan-Meier method. They are applied to analogs of 2 real clinical trials, one of which serves as the external control source for the other. The performances of these methods are compared based on various factors, including type I error rate, power, bias, mean squared error, and effective historical sample size.

Key Words: Bayesian, dynamic borrowing, clinical trial, propensity score

1. Introduction

Dynamic borrowing of external patient data to augment clinical trial endpoints offers several advantages: it allows for earlier reading of trial results for endpoints with long follow-up periods, decreases the number of patients enrolled in placebo arms, and potentially reduces operating budget. Consequently, such approaches benefit the development of clinical trials.

To achieve successful dynamic borrowing, the quality of external data is paramount. Concurrent clinical trials containing control patients from the same investigational sites and adhering to the same inclusion/exclusion criteria are generally preferred over historical clinical trial data or real-world data (RWD). This preference arises because concurrent trials exhibit minimal secular trends and geographic differences, thereby reducing the impact of confounding factors when comparing treatment and control arms. The quality of data is particularly critical when the endpoint to be augmented is a key secondary endpoint of the internal clinical trial, and when the focus is on primary analysis rather than sensitivity analyses.

In this project, three dynamic borrowing methods are selected and compared to utilize one concurrent clinical trial external control data source to augment the internal clinical trial's overall survival, which is a time-to-event (TTE) endpoint.

2. Methods

This paper discusses three dynamic borrowing methods that are suitable for incorporating individual control patient data from a concurrent clinical trial.

2.1 Method 1: Commensurate Prior Approach

For a parameter of interest θ , the commensurate prior is of the form (2011 Hobbs):

$$\pi(\theta|D_0, \theta_0, \tau) \propto L(\theta_0|D_0) \pi(\theta|\theta_0, \tau)\pi_0(\theta)$$

$L(\theta_0|D_0)$ stands for the likelihood function of historical data; D_0 and D represents data from historical and current trial; $\pi_0(\theta)$ is the initial prior.

This Bayesian hierarchical model is assuming $\theta \sim \mathcal{N}(\theta_0, \frac{1}{\tau})$, where $\tau = 1/\sigma^2$, and σ^2 is the between-trial variance= $\text{var}(\theta|\theta_0)$. This τ is named commensurability parameter because:

- As τ approaches 0, the commensurate prior $\pi(\theta|D_0, \theta_0, \tau) \rightarrow \pi_0(\theta)$, effectively ignoring the historical data.
- As τ approaches ∞ , $\theta \rightarrow \theta_0$ so commensurate prior $\rightarrow L(\theta|D_0)\pi_0(\theta)$, recovering the result obtained from pooling the two datasets.

For TTE (t) assumed to follow a Weibull distribution below, commensurate prior approach can also be applied (Lewis et al 2019):

$$f(t; k_i, v) = \frac{v}{k_i} \left(\frac{t}{k_i}\right)^{v-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{k_i}\right)^v}$$

- v : shape parameter, $v=1$ in exponential distribution;
- k : scale parameter; alternative parametrization of scale parameter: $\lambda_i = \left(\frac{1}{k_i}\right)^v$;

To incorporate covariates, let $\lambda_i = e^{z_i\beta + x_i\gamma}$,

Proportional hazards models: $h_i(t, v, \beta, \gamma) = v e^{z_i\beta + x_i\gamma} t^{v-1}$

z_i : a vector of group indicators for subject i , 1st variable indicating in internal trial or not, 2nd variable indicating external or not, 3rd variable indicating treatment or not ([1, 0, 0]: internal control; [0, 1, 0]: external control; [1, 0, 1]: treatment)

β : coefficient vector for indicator variables, [β_{IC} , β_{EC} , β_{Trt-IC}]

γ : coefficient vector for covariates

Group	Indicator variable z_k	Hazard Rates	Hazard Ratios
Internal Control	[1, 0, 0]	$v t^{v-1} e^{\beta_{IC} + x_k \gamma}$	Reference
External Control	[0, 1, 0]	$v t^{v-1} e^{\beta_{EC} + x_k \gamma}$	$driftHR = e^{\beta_{EC} - \beta_{IC}}$
Treatment	[1, 0, 1]	$v t^{v-1} e^{\beta_{IC} + \beta_{Trt-IC} + x_k \gamma}$	$HR = e^{\beta_{Trt-IC}}$

Parameters and priors:

- $\beta_{Trt-IC} \sim \text{normal}(0, 1000)$
- $\beta_{EC} \sim \text{normal}(0, 1000)$
- $\beta_{IC} | \beta_{EC} \sim \text{normal}\left(\beta_{EC}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{\tau}}\right)$,

precision= τ , commensurability parameter

Hyper parameter and hyperprior:

prior of $\tau \sim \text{gamma}(\text{shape} = 0.001, \text{rate} = 0.001)$ shows an example of a largely uninformative prior of the commensurability parameter. Seeing from **Figure 1**, this conservative prior is showing more density at smaller τ , representing a likely large commensurability/similarity between external and internal control data, leading to less borrowing than an aggressive prior as a Gamma distribution (shape=1, rate=0.001), which indicates larger probability at small τ , better commensurability/similarity, thus more borrowing.

This method is based on a Bayesian hierarchical model, assuming Weibull distributions, and adjusting for covariates. Propensity score (PS) is being adjusted in the model (Please note that the power of PS-adjusted model is lower than that of covariates-adjusted model). This method can be implemented using R package `psborrow2`. The ‘nominal number to borrow’ cannot determine in advance and the extent of borrowing is decided by the prior of commensurability parameter, as well as the drift between internal and external data. Therefore, control arm outcomes from both internal and external trials are needed to determine extent to borrow.

Figure 1 Aggressive vs conservative prior of τ

2.2 Method 2 Resampling Approach (Li et al 2022)

This frequentist method starts with generating the logarithm of hazard ratio ($\log(\text{HR})$) for two control arms (internal control Arm B and external control Arm E) by a resampling method over M replicates. For $m = 1$ to M (i.e., 1,000):

- Randomly draw $0.75 * n_B$ subjects from Arm B without replacement.
- Match subjects in external arm E to selected subjects from B in a 1:1 ratio using PS
- Calculate the $\log(\text{HR})$ by adjusting the covariates, denoted as $\hat{\tau}_m$.

The empirical distribution of $\log(\text{HR})$ determines the weight based on these rules:

- $S(B, E) = \frac{2}{M} \min\{\sum_{m=1}^M 1_{(\hat{\tau}_m > 0)}, \sum_{m=1}^M 1_{(\hat{\tau}_m < 0)}\}$ as the measure of combinability between two control arms.
- For a balanced pair of two control arms, the chances of getting positive and negative $\log(\text{HR})$ are $\sim 50\%$, resulting the value $S(B, E)$ closer to $1 = \frac{2}{M} \times \frac{M}{2}$.
- $w = \begin{cases} S(B, E), & \text{for } S(B, E) > p_{cutoff} \\ 0, & \text{for } S(B, E) \leq p_{cutoff} \end{cases}$, where w ranges from 0 to 1.

The tuning mechanism of how much to borrow is the weighted likelihood using weights between 0 and 1. And the weights are determined by similarity parameter $S(B, E)$, which controls the extent of borrowing. PS is used to determine the matched samples used to calculate the $\log(\text{HR})$ while resampling. Similar to commensurate prior approach, the ‘nominal number to borrow’ cannot be determined in advance; and control arm outcomes from both internal and external trials are needed to determine the extent to borrow.

2.3 Method 3 PSKM (Chen et al. 2022)

In this propensity score-integrated frequentist approach (using single-arm as an example), survival function is estimated by weighted KM estimator, with weights defined by similarity of PS distribution for each stratum.

PSKM estimator for k-th stratum:
$$\hat{S}_k^w(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t < t_{1,k} \\ \prod_{j:t_{j,k} \leq t} \left[1 - \frac{d_{j,k}^w}{Y_{j,k}^w} \right] & \text{if } t \geq t_{1,k} \end{cases}$$

$$w_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Z_i = 1 \\ \min\left(\frac{Ar_k}{n_{k,0} \sum_{k'=1}^K r_{k'}}, 1\right) & \text{if } Z_i = 0, K_i = k \\ 0 & \text{if } Z_i = 0, K_i \neq k \end{cases}$$

$$r_k = \int_0^1 \min[g_{k,0}(u), g_{k,1}(u)] du$$

k: stratum, $t_{1,k}$: first observed event time, $d_{j,k}^w$: number of events weighted by w_i , $Y_{j,k}^w$: number of subjects at risk weighted by w_i , A: nominal number to be borrowed (determined, not calculated), r_k : similarity measure, defined as overlapping area of density curves of PSs in external and internal trial. For RCT, log rank test is used to evaluate difference in survival between arms. This approach is based on frequentist non-parametric modeling. The tuning mechanism to control the extent to borrow is the KM pseudo-likelihood in which number of events and number of subjects at risk are weighted. PS is used to define strata and calculate the similarity measure, in order to calculate weights. Different to the other 2 approaches, ‘nominal number to borrow’ can be determined in advance, and the weight determination does not need outcome data at all. This approach can be implemented with R package psrwe.

2.4 Operating characteristics

In order to compare the three approaches for the same clinical scenarios, we can calculate these operating characteristics: type I error rate (compared to 0.025); power; bias of HR, mean squared error, and effective historical sample size (EHSS). The formulas are shown as below, with ‘IC’ representing internal control and ‘Int’ representing the population to calculate the effect estimate for.

$$\text{Bias} = E(\text{estimated effect from posterior} - \text{true effect})$$

- Mean Squared error (MSE) of HR

$$\text{MSE} = E((\text{estimated effect} - \text{true effect})^2) = (\text{Bias})^2 + \text{Variance}$$

- Effective Historical Sample Size (EHSS)

$$\text{EHSS} = N_{Int} \left(\frac{\text{Prec}(\beta_{Trt-IC} | \text{Borrowing})}{\text{Prec}(\beta_{Trt-IC} | \text{No Borrowing})} - 1 \right)$$

3. Case Example Setting

The motivating example of this paper are based on two real clinical trials, both Phase III, open label, randomized controlled trials (RCT) sponsored by Bristol Myers Squibb (BMS) in 2023, for patients of the same disease and same eligibility criteria. The control arms are using the same standard care drug of the same dosage.

There are 4 clinical trial scenarios and 5 borrowing scenarios:

	Drift HR = 1 (no diff in ext and int controls)	Drift HR=1.05 (144m vs. 137m, ext control is "sicker" than int control)
HR=1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cox model with no borrowing + covariate adjustment psborrow2: Dynamic borrowing (commensurate prior) using a conservative prior + covariate adjustment 	
HR=0 .77	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resampling method + covariate adjustment PSKM: PS-integrated log-rank test (ps stratification; pre-specified n=100, 5 strata) Full borrowing (pooling) using a Bayesian model + covariate adjustment 	

10,000 simulation replicates per borrowing time per scenario are performed. Other simulation inputs include mean, variance, covariance of baseline confounding factors, enrollment rate, inclusion and exclusion after simulation.

3. Simulation Results

3.1 Type I Error Rate

- With no drift HR, all methods at any of the 3 borrowing timepoints have controlled type I error rates.
- With moderate drift HR, full borrowing exhibits inflated type I error rates.
- With moderate drift HR, type I error rates increase with longer follow-up time.

3.2 Power

- Full borrowing > Commensurate prior method > PSKM > Resampling method > No borrowing

3.3 Bias

- Resampling method has a similar bias as no borrowing.
- With moderate drift HR, full borrowing has a lower HR/a stronger treatment effect given full borrowing borrows more external control data that favor rejecting the null.

3.4 MSE

- Full borrowing has the smallest MSE while the other three methods have similar MSEs.
- Smaller MSE is associated with longer follow-up time.

3.5 Effective Historical Sample Size

- EHSS is consistent with power. The higher the power is, the higher EHSS is.
- Notably, EHSS can only be compared across different methods within the same dataset.

4. Discussion

The pros and cons of the three approaches are summarized in the following table.

	Commensurate Prior + Covariates Adjustment Method	Resampling Method	PSKM / PS-integrated log-rank test
Pros	✓ Easy implementation in R or R package available		
	✓ Results are straightforward and easy to interpret		✓ Nominal number to be borrowed can be determined in advance
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Controlled type I error rate when no drift HR is present ✓ Highest power and EHSS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Controlled type I error rate ✓ Lower bias 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Lowest type I error rate when no drift HR is present ✓ Higher power
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inflated type I error rate when moderate drift HR is present • Time-consuming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower power and EHSS in general 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No HR estimate
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommended for no drift HR 	Recommended for moderate drift HR	Recommended for no drift HR and HR estimate is not a requirement

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